

Analyze Cyber Attacks in Cloud Cryptography and Short Comings in Blockchain Cryptocurrency

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Abstract: Technological improvements have happened in companies digitalizing various elements of their actions. The threat landscape of cyber-attacks is rapidly changing. The possible consequence of such attacks is unknown because there is a lack of useful metrics, tools and frameworks to explain and evaluate the harm industries suffer from cyber-attacks. Cyber-attacks are not new to IoT, but as IoT will be strongly mixed in our days and communities, it is becoming important to step up and take cyber security severely. Hence, there is a real need to secure IoT, resulting in a need to comprehensively recognize the warnings and attacks on IoT infrastructure. The paper's main objective is to investigate the impact of the cyber-attacks in the common cyber framework and analyze the blockchain crypto-currency architecture to evaluate the weaknesses and safety representation. The security of cryptocurrency heavily relies on the incentive-compatible Proof of Authority (PoA) based on distributed consensus protocol; a consensus algorithm type based on the reputation of trusted parties in a blockchain network. This paper introduces Proof of Authority (PoA) based distributed consensus protocol and a novel blockchain-based decentralized federation model that embodies quality verification for cloud providers who lease computing resources from each other.

Keywords: Blockchain security, Cryptocurrency, Internet of Things, Cloud service, Proof of Authority.

I. INTRODUCTION

The recent fast growth of the Internet of Things (IoT)[1] and its capacity to perform certain services have performed it the fastest developing technology, significantly affecting social lifestyles and business conditions. The Internet of Things has slowly infiltrated all components of human life today, including training, healthcare, and businesses, including collecting sensitive data about people and businesses, financial records transactions, product growth, and marketing. The extensive generation of associated devices within the Internet of Things has commenced high requirements for robust protection in response to the growing requirement for tens of millions or possibly billions of associated devices and offerings internationally [2]. The number of threats is increasing daily, and the attacks are increasing in scope and complexity. The number of potential attackers and the growing network size are not the most practical. Still, the equipment available to potential attackers has also become more advanced, efficient, and powerful [3]. Therefore, for the Internet of Things to achieve its full potential, it needs to be secure against threats and vulnerabilities. Security has been described as a way to protect an item from physical harm, unauthorized entry, theft, or loss, with the help of maintaining excessive confidentiality and integrity of facts about the item and establishing facts about that item. Any time. It is necessary.

Today, cryptocurrency has grown a buzzword in both business and academia. As one of the common strong cryptocurrencies, Bitcoin has enjoyed significant compliance with its capital market that produced \$10 billion in 2016 [4]. With a specially produced form of data storage, transactions on the Bitcoin network may wish to proceed without any service. The primary generation to make Bitcoin is the blockchain, first introduced in 2008 and executed in 2009 [5]. Blockchain can appear as a public record, and all authorized transactions are kept in the block list. This category is growing as new blocks are continually being attached to it. Asymmetric encryption and shared consensus algorithms have been implemented for user security and public ledger compatibility. The blockchain age frequently has the essential features of decentralization, resolution, anonymity, and audibility. With these trends, blockchain can significantly buy fees and improve efficiency.

Blockchain can be applied for various financial contributions, including virtual property, online transfers, and shipping. Furthermore, it can also be achieved in other areas, including smart contracts [6], public contributions [7], and the Internet of Things (IoT).

The transaction can be accomplished using automated miners for smart contracts as soon as the transaction is performed on the blockchain. Although blockchain technology can improve targeted Internet systems globally, it allows various challenging technical conditions. First of all, scalability is a huge challenge. The bitcoin block is now restricted to at least one megabyte, while the block is mined roughly every ten minutes. Thus, the Bitcoin network is limited to seven transaction fees based on the second and cannot handle frequent excessive trading. However, larger blocks indicate a larger storage area and slower spread within the network. This will begin to centralise, as fewer users will like to operate one of these huge blocks. Hence, trade-offs between block length

and security were a challenging task. Second, it has been described that miner may want to create sales above their fair share through a self-centred mining method. Miners cover their mined blocks to get more sales within the destination. In this way, the branches must be regularly closed, which makes blockchain development difficult. Therefore, should recommend some answers to solve this problem.

BLOCKCHAIN ARCHITECTURE

Fig.1 An example of Blockchain which consists of a continuous sequence of blocks.

Fig.2 Block structure

Blockchain is a chain of blocks that includes a full list of transaction facts like a common public ledger. Figure 1 shows an example of a blockchain. With the past block's hash in the block header, the block includes only one highlight block. It is worth remarking that hashes of uncle blocks (children of the block ancestors) would also be stored on the ethereum Blockchain. The first blockchain block is known as the configuration block that does not include a select block. Then we describe the inside of the blockchain in detail.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows

- We recommend a Proof of Authority (PoA) based distributed consensus protocol to present safety.
- We recommended a Blockchain-based distributed cloud storage design to produce more reliable and secure cloud storage assistance for companies or individual users.
- We customize a genetic algorithm to determine the file block replica situation problem among various users and data centres in the distributed cloud storage conditions.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Cloud storage is a network generation method for sharing assets with associated IT skills, critical for business or personal users. In particular, traditional cloud storage protection strategies include knowledge about log encryption, access management, and many more. Recently, Software-Defined Storage (SDS) integrated several cloud storage services that are dispensed to address the issue that a separate cloud cannot meet user needs.

Nguyen et al. [2020] Blockchain technology has become what is moving the world through a hurricane, and Blockchain emerged as a disruptive technology for the subsequent generation of various commercial software. In this paper, a new model for integrating Blockchain and Cloud of Things, known as BCoT, is widely emerging as a promising enabler for various public service situations. This article provided an up-to-date overview of BCoT integration to give regular readers an overview of BCoT in many aspects: experience, motivation, and embedded architecture. They also provided an in-depth survey of BCoT packages across different use case areas: smart healthcare, smart cities, smart transportation, and smart industry.

WissamZaki et al. [2020] Cloud computing has become a completely useful generation in our daily existence; this computing uses the internet to provide software and transmit and keep facts. It becomes necessary to provide an environment that protects applications and records inside this cloud; networks should be protocols. That used powerful algorithms to protect it. This article mentioned some of them, and compared to others, factual security and encryption became among the most important discoveries. Although improved in the days of wine completely separately, this fact confirmed a close connection between them.

Mohamed MounirMoussa et al.[2020] It was looked at the implementation and organization techniques associated with dew computing, where processing was added even towards the user compared to the different IoT computing paradigms. This document aims to assess IoT threats and the use of deep field technology to counter cyber anomalies and then validate them by analyzing their metrics. They evaluated the state of the variable stats between the cloud and the relevant vehicle-embedded dew stop devices. They used a modified version of Stacked Autoencoder that improved detection accuracy for specific attacks, using school information loss as a threshold.

Aditi Patel et al. [2020] An emerging era has been suggested offering computer services along with online business software and online data storage. Deployed cloud enables an unauthorized operating environment where business expenses are reduced, data is provided, real security, etc. As many companies embrace cloud computing, attackers exploit the cloud to achieve unauthorized manipulation of valuable records stored in it. The evolution from traditional computing to the cloud has brought many security challenges for every customer and vendor. Online cloud service providers have made various offers using various technologies, which generate distinct security threats.

Chengpeng Xia et al. [2018] An incentive is provided to encourage nearby servers to serve cellular clients for the mobile blockchain software. They formulated the problem as a useful and useful resource allocation problem, then proposed a public sale of three levels of beneficial implementation of resource allocation tailored to the cellular blockchain, and brought in a specific purchasing mechanism to encourage customers smartphones. It also showed that his auction scheme turned out to be honest, personal sanity and athletic performance. The proposed scheme was compared with the mechanisms of TACD and HAF, and the simulation results showed that appropriate social status with the help of its scheme was better than the mechanisms of TACD and HAF.

Aydogan et al. [2017] Mobile attack techniques can be categorized as primarily software-based attacks and frequency-based attacks. Utility-based assaults have been radically reviewed in the literature. However, frequency-based attacks on mobile phones have not been thoroughly tested. This panel experimentally attacks an Android cell phone using a radio circuit based primarily on a simple application. They have developed a "Mobile Hack Master Builder" to control your Android smartphone remotely. SMS information and photos may be received within the cell phone using this device. On the contrary, after going out for a walk with a cellular smartphone application, it can control the virtual camera of the mobile phones to take pictures and download them to the chassis of our laptop.

Jiaying et al. [2017] suggested Blockchain-based security architecture for distributed cloud storage. With the improvement of the ICT industry, the number of events produced has grown exponentially, which has increased the demand for storage capacity. Due to the limited garage capacity of customer terminals, more and more software prefers to upload statistics to cloud platforms. However, it is known that you cannot forget about security in current cloud garage architectures. Driven by the growing popularity of the emerging blockchain age, they have proposed Blockchain-based security architecture for out-of-pocket cloud storage.

Garay et al. [2017] presented the first formal analysis of the functionality of (re)calculating the Bitcoin target in a crypto site, that is, against all potential adversaries who seek to subvert the properties of the protocol. They extend the q-delimited synchronous model of the Bitcoin Pillar Protocol (Eurocrypt 2015), which rolls out the simple houses of Bitcoin's underlying Blockchain data structure and demonstrates how a robust public transaction ledger can be built at its peak to environments that can enter or suspend matches each round.

III. TYPES OF CYBER ATTACKS IN CLOUD CRYPTOGRAPHY

Cyber attacks in cloud computing tend to generate most of the vulnerabilities found in the cloud's core structural additions. These weaknesses and vulnerabilities have attracted hobbies from various attack profiles ranging from children of scripts to APT. Several cyberattacks are seen in many cloud environments that exploit vulnerabilities in cloud extensions or misconfigurations based on the design sample. All of these attacks violate at least one of the principles of the CIA's Trinity. Most attacks are directed at cloud components within a particular layer or across different layers. Therefore, the attacks considered from now on represent both multi-

stage attacks within a layer and between layers. Bye, they use some form of pivot nodes to boost the attack. The intent of a specific attack is different from the alternative.

There are various cyber-attacks involved in cloud cryptography listed below

1. Hyperjacking
2. Honest but Curious Server
3. Link Aggregation Attack (DoS type attack)
4. Side Channel Attack
5. VM Migration Attack:
6. VM Escape Attack
7. MITC Attack
8. XML - HTTP DOS

IV. VARIOUS SHORTCOMINGS IN CRYPTOCURRENCY

There are a few shortcomings related to crypto-currency are given below

a) Scalability

Probably the biggest issues with cryptocurrencies are the volume issues that can arise. While the wide variety and adoption of virtual currencies are unexpectedly increasing, it is dwarfed by the number of transactions that cost so much, VISA, that comes in every day. Moreover, transaction rate is another important metric that cryptocurrencies cannot compete with in the same arena as players like VISA and Mastercard until the infrastructure that provides this technology is greatly expanded.

b) Cyber security issues

As a virtual technology, cryptocurrencies can be a problem for cybersecurity breaches and can fall into the hands of hackers. We've already seen evidence of this, with some ICOs hacked and costing buyers tens of millions of dollars this summer alone (this kind of raid alone resulted in a \$473 million loss). Mitigating this may require keeping the security infrastructure uninterrupted. Still, we are already seeing many players tackle this without delay and use more robust cyber security features beyond those used in the traditional banking industries.

c) Price volatility and lack of inherent value

Price volatility, linked to an inherent lack of value, is a primary annoyance and one of the details that Buffett has primarily been referring to in the past few weeks while describing the cryptocurrency environment as a bubble. However, it is a fundamental situation that can be overcome by linking the price of a foreign cryptocurrency directly to tangible and intangible properties (as we have seen some new players do with diamonds or energy derivatives). High adoption should enhance customer confidence and reduce this volatility.

d) High volatility and potential for large losses

The annualized monthly percentage volatility of trading within the bitcoin price in US dollars has been set at 90% measured over the past five years. This compares to the annual volatility of monthly percentage changes in the S&P 500 and gold rate at 15.3% and 13.4%, respectively. To give some insight into what this volatility might suggest to an investor, consider the range of returns: the maximum monthly returns for bitcoin in the 60 months to the end of December 2020 have changed to 76.1% and the minimum -37.6%. The timing of investing in bitcoin or other cryptocurrencies can have a significant impact on completed returns.

e) Endless potential supply

While it is very true that sooner or later, the variety of bitcoins produced will be set at 21 million different cryptocurrencies and also have a limited supply built into their protocols, there is currently nothing stopping a wide range of new cryptocurrencies from developing. Therefore, cryptocurrency delivery is likely to be unlimited. It is also worth noting that several important banks are exploring the opportunity to launch their cryptocurrency, which could weaken private issuance.

f) Poor store of value and limited acceptance

While Bitcoin and a few different cryptocurrencies are currently enshrined via a growing variety of fee structures, the number of places you can exchange cryptocurrencies for actual items or services is still very limited. For similar reasons, the inherent volatility of cryptocurrencies makes them a terrible store of value.

When converted into a base currency for an individual, the cost of cryptocurrencies will vary significantly, even during the day.

g) Unregulated and unbacked

Cryptocurrency is a private sector build with no approved supervision or regulation. This approach is that cryptocurrencies are widely open to being exploited by criminals to deceive unsuspecting investors. A 2019 educational study found that 25% of bitcoin customers are concerned about illegal interests, and 46% of bitcoin transactions are related to illegal activities.

V. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Proof of Authority (PoA) consensus algorithm

Proof of Authority (PoA) is a type of consensus algorithm primarily based on the popularity of affiliate parties in a blockchain network. It is a completely new consensus algorithm organization that offers high performance and fault tolerance. In PoA, the advantages of creating new blocks are given to nodes that have proven their authority. A node must provide pre-authentication to gain this authority and sufficient authentication to create new blocks.

PoA is a set of rules for consensus within the blockchain that proposes a robust and effective answer to the privacy of facts in blockchain networks. The PoA algorithm uses the value of identities to enforce security by personally validating nodes set to be trusted. The Proof of Authority set of rules relies on various block validators, making it a remarkably scalable device. Blocks and transactions are viewed with the help of pre-approved peers who act as device admins. The proof of authority model allows organizations to maintain their privacy while taking advantage of blockchain technology. Microsoft Azure is an instance in which PoA is implemented. The Azure platform offers answers to non-public blockchain networks without the local currency “fuel” of ether, as there is no need for mining. Smart contracts are pieces of software or code on the blockchain managed by a P2P network of computer systems. Smart contracts are human rights monitoring teams that provide a framework for coordinating and enforcing agreements between individuals in a community without the need for traditional criminal contracts. They can be used to implement simple agreements between parties, company bylaws, or to create tokens. In the context of a blockchain, smart contracts are a public, private boundary built into the blockchain, which can receive or execute transactions as multiple parameters (transactions can be rejected or require unique arguments for a function), which can act as an immutable element. The purpose of smart contracts is to act like a “computerized transaction protocol that implements the agreement's provisions”.

The PoA protocol is that there is a decentralized network of cryptocurrencies whose security mainly depends on a combination of Proof of Work and Proof of Stake. In terms of fashion, fully Proof of Work-based protocols provide decision-making power to entities that perform computational responsibilities, even as fully Proof-of-stake-based protocols provide decision-making power to entities that maintain participation in the device.

PoA algorithms are based on a set of N trusted nodes called governance. Each authority is diagnosed with the help of unique identification, and most of them are considered to be honest, particularly at least $N = 2 + 1$. Authorities come to a consensus to order outgoing transactions through customers. The consensus on activity program algorithms is based on the mining rotation scheme, a widely used approach to equitably allocating responsibility for the emergence of blocks between authorities. The time is divided into steps, each of which has an expert chosen to be the mining leader.

It is an eco-friendly mechanism for personal blockchains and was developed with the help of Ethereum co-founder and former CTO Gavin Wood in 2017. The PoA consensus algorithm is primarily based on the cost of identities within the community and various devices; Auditors are not betting on assets but their identities and reputation. Therefore, PoA Blockchain networks are protected by validation nodes that can be arbitrarily selected as honest events.

The Proof of Authority model runs on a powerful and fast set of block validation tools, making it an easily scalable blockchain device because transactions are verified with the help of already accepted community contributors. The PoA consensus rule set can be used in packets that include delivery chains or exchange networks because the actual identities of the nodes are considered trusted.

PoA consensus algorithm

Step 1: Each miner uses her hash power to try to generate an empty block header.

Step 2: When a miner succeeds in generating an empty block header, meaning that the hash of her block header data is smaller than the current difficulty target.

Step 3: All the network nodes regard the hash of this block header as data that deterministically derives N pseudorandom stakeholders.

Step 4: Every stakeholder who is online checks whether the empty block header that the miner broadcasted is valid, meaning that it contains the hash of the previous block and meets the current difficulty.

Step 5: The Nth stakeholder broadcasts the wrapped block to the network, and when the other nodes see that this wrapped block is valid according to the above, they consider it a legitimate extension of the blockchain.

Step 6: The fees from the transactions that the Nth stakeholder collected are shared between the miner and the N lucky stakeholders.

PoA mechanism makes it possible to defend against this attack because network nodes are pre-authenticated, block generation rights can be granted only to nodes that can withstand DoS attacks.

Use of Cryptography in Blockchain

Blockchain uses types of encryption algorithms, asymmetric key algorithms, and hash functions. The hash functions are used to provide the ability to view one blockchain per player, and Blockchains generally use the SHA-256 hash rule set as the hash function.

Basic architecture for Cryptocurrency:

Fig.3 Basic architecture for cryptocurrency

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the experimental are conducted using python 3.7 programming language and the KDD dataset used with 5 rows and 42 columns to perform the analysis of the previous algorithm of RNN (recurrent neural network).

```

Python 3.7.3 (64-bit)
Python 3.7.3 (v3.7.3:ef4ec6d12, Mar 25 2019, 22:22:05) [MSC v.1916 64 bit (AMD64)] on win32
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> import numpy as np
>>> import pandas as pd
>>> import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
>>> import time
>>> import datetime
>>>
>>> df = pd.read_csv('C:/Users/sravan/Desktop/2021/satya/block chain/obj1/dataset.csv')
>>> df.head()
   0  tcp  private  REJ    0.1    0.2  0.3  0.4  ...  0.061  0.003  0.004  0.005  0.006  1.002  1.003  anomaly
1  0  tcp  private  REJ    0    0  0  0  ...  0.06  0.00  0.00  0.00  0.00  0.00  1.00  1.00  anomaly
2  2  tcp  ftp_data  SF  12983  0  0  0  ...  0.04  0.61  0.02  0.00  0.00  0.00  0.00  normal
3  0  icmp  eco_i    SF    20    0  0  0  ...  0.00  1.00  0.28  0.00  0.00  0.00  0.00  anomaly
4  1  tcp  telnet   RSTO    0    15  0  0  ...  0.17  0.03  0.02  0.00  0.00  0.83  0.71  anomaly
5  0  tcp  http    SF    267  14515  0  0  ...  0.00  0.01  0.03  0.01  0.00  0.00  0.00  normal

[5 rows x 42 columns]
>>>
    
```

Fig.4 Identifying the cyber attacks on block chain intrusion for previous RNN method

Fig.4 indicates the data set with the features for identifying the cyber-attacks on block chain intrusion.

```
Python 3.7 (64-bit)
dst_host_same_srv_rate dst_host_diff_srv_rate \
0 0.06 0.00
1 0.04 0.61
2 0.00 1.00
3 0.17 0.83
4 0.00 0.01

dst_host_same_src_port_rate dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate \
0 0.00 0.00
1 0.02 0.00
2 0.25 0.00
3 0.02 0.00
4 0.03 0.01

dst_host_serror_rate dst_host_srv_serror_rate dst_host_rerror_rate \
0 0.0 1.00 1.00
1 0.0 0.00 0.00
2 0.0 0.00 0.00
3 0.0 0.83 0.71
4 0.0 0.00 0.00

class
0 anomaly
1 normal
2 anomaly
3 anomaly
4 normal
>>>
```

Fig.5: working with the class labels from the data

```
Python 3.7 (64-bit)
dst_host_same_src_port_rate dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate \
0 0.00 0.00
1 0.02 0.00
2 0.25 0.00
3 0.02 0.00
4 0.03 0.01

dst_host_serror_rate dst_host_srv_serror_rate dst_host_rerror_rate \
0 0.0 1.00 1.00
1 0.0 0.00 0.00
2 0.0 0.00 0.00
3 0.0 0.83 0.71
4 0.0 0.00 0.00

class
0 anomaly
1 normal
2 anomaly
3 anomaly
4 normal
>>> df_new = df
>>> from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
>>> labelencoder = LabelEncoder()
>>> df_new['protocol_type'] = labelencoder.fit_transform(df_new['protocol_type'])
>>> df_new['service'] = labelencoder.fit_transform(df_new['service'])
>>> df_new['flag'] = labelencoder.fit_transform(df_new['flag'])
>>> df_new['class'] = labelencoder.fit_transform(df_new['class'])
>>>
```

Fig.6 label encoder which works on encoding the classified label for the process of intrusion

Fig.7 Support features for the intrusion of previous method

```
Python 3.7 (64-bit)
NameError: name 'y_pred' is not defined
>>> from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix
>>> print(classification_report(y_test, predictions))
precision recall f1-score support
0 0.74 1.00 0.85 2532
1 0.99 0.55 0.71 1977
accuracy 0.87 0.77 0.80 4509
macro avg 0.87 0.77 0.78 4509
weighted avg 0.85 0.80 0.79 4509
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
```

Fig.8 Accuracy of the model with the prediction and rate


```
0      0.74      1.00      0.85      2532
1      0.99      0.55      0.71      1977
accuracy
macro avg      0.87      0.77      0.80      4509
weighted avg   0.85      0.80      0.79      4509
>>>
```

Fig.9 Accuracy for previous method

VII.CONCLUSION

Cloud computing is seen as the future of computing and storage technology, and the work carried out with blockchain technology in the next era is studied in this paper. Considering these security issues, we analyzed the existing deep learning-based RNN model with experimental steps that increased the integrity of the statistics. The emergence of connected devices and computing is the need for cloud computing in its current form. We can say that the previous method achieved 80% accuracy with prediction and rate by analyzing the experiment. Further, enhance the approach to building a Blockchain-based secure and decentralized access control network on a Cloud platform.

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